

**ACTIVITIES OF THE SHANGHAI COOPERATION ORGANIZATION
IN 2016-2024**

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Strengthening the “Shanghai Spirit” – a unique experience of multilateral cooperation that reflects our common values, our aspiration for common development, and our respect for cultural diversity – is more important than ever today.

Sh.M.Mirziyoyev

Abstract: By 2024, the SCO had emerged as an organization that made a significant contribution to the global and economic situation, economic and social development. At the same time, internal regulatory issues, the need for members to control and protect their own interests, and to take important measures against security threats became more urgent.

Key words: Shanghai Cooperation Organization, SCO, geopolitical, economic, social, UN Security Council, objectivity, causality.

The topic of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization remains one of the new and relevant topics not only for the history of international relations, but also for the history of its member states. This is because the global problems that are currently occurring in the world - the world economic crisis, international tensions, terrorism, drug trafficking, separatism, environmental degradation on the one hand, and economic integration on the other - cannot be solved by a single state in the region alone. To solve this, there is a need for the activities of organizations such as the SCO in international cooperation.

“Speaking of the role of the SCO in implementing all these complex tasks, it is extremely important to turn it into an open, efficient and effective organization that is

as appropriate to the situation and capabilities of its participants as possible. As an international political association, the SCO deals not only with regional problems, but also with other international and regional problems. Constant changes in the world encourage the organization to work more actively. Before our eyes, profound processes are taking place that are fundamentally changing the geopolitical, economic, social, and information and communication landscape of the modern world.

Therefore, it is very important for us to work together within the SCO to develop common approaches to integration and the creation of a regional market. I am sure that the resolution of these issues will equally correspond to the fundamental interests of all SCO member states.

This is explained by an assessment of the modern specifics of economic cooperation within the SCO and its importance for the development of the participating states. Currently, there is no clear idea of how the SCO will develop in the future: will multilateral economic integration between the participating states really take place or will the organization remain an international institution of bilateral cooperation. In the field of economic cooperation, in order to determine its promising directions, as well as issues of conflict of interests of the participating states in the economic and political spheres, practical achievements require constant updating. The study of the SCO is relevant from the point of view of analyzing the development trends of world territoriality, in particular, from the point of view of cooperation between individual territorial associations of states. Of course, studying the SCO is also important for Russia's interests in developing one or another regional cooperation project in Eurasia.

Uzbekistan, having gained independence, adopted its own constitution as a sovereign state and, based on it, became a full-fledged subject of the system of international relations of Uzbekistan. We can observe this in Uzbekistan's membership in the SCO, which has become an influential organization in the system of international relations. In this regard, President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev reacts as follows: "Today, we have every reason to say that the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, established in

2001, has become an influential international structure of modern geopolitics in a historically short time.”

If we briefly look at the history of the organization, the SCO was initially called the “Shanghai Five”, and as a result of Uzbekistan's membership in it, its geography expanded further.

Speaking about interstate cooperation within the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, there is every reason to ensure that the main political, economic and military-technical powers of this organization, which are currently the permanent members of the UN Security Council - Russia, China and India, are the main ones and will remain so in the future.

The SCO, as an international organization, believes that its main direction is to ensure security and further develop economic relations. The organization does not aim to create military blocs or undermine the security of other countries. In particular, Sh.M. Mirziyoyev expressed the following opinion at the SCO summit held in Samarkand on September 16, 2022.

“We firmly believe that the main pillars, the most important directions supporting the SCO structure should be security and economy. Only by relying on these two pillars, or, so to speak, the two wheels of the cart, can the effectiveness of the SCO’s activities and its international influence be ensured, in line with the rapidly changing world situation.”

Today, the SCO member states have a population of more than 3.4 billion people, and geographically, they cover a very vast territory, including Russia, China, India, Kazakhstan, Pakistan and Uzbekistan.

More than ten years have passed since its official formation and today, the SCO, which has embarked on a path of development, has carried out a lot of work at the regional and international levels during this period, proceeding from its principles. First of all, the structural structure of the organization has improved. The agreement that laid the foundation stone for resolving the border disputes between the two countries just yesterday has reached the level of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization. In addition,

one of the main goals of the SCO is to strive for stability and peace in the region and the world. During its activity, a lot of work has been done within the framework of the SCO in this area.

In order to scientifically study and reveal the role and place of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization in the modern system of international relations, in particular in ensuring regional stability in Central Asia, the scientific research of foreign research and "think tanks", political scientists, analysts and theorists, political and analytical literature published in Uzbekistan and abroad were studied.

The scientific works of Uzbek researchers mainly cover the SCO's role in ensuring security and stability in the region, the approaches of China and Russia in this structure. In particular, the fundamental work of the famous scientist A. Khodjayev entitled "The Chinese Factor in Central Asia" reveals in detail the role of the SCO within the framework of the analysis of the PRC's strategy towards the region. F. Tolipov studied the role of the organization in geopolitical processes in the region, and I. Bekmurotov, M. Sharipov and A. Mukhamedjanov studied the role of the SCO in ensuring security and stability in the Central and South Asian regions. Historians M. Rakhimov studied the features of the institutional development of the organization, and S. Rakhimov studied the historical aspects of Uzbekistan-SCO cooperation.

The aim of the study is to scientifically analyze the position of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization member states in world politics and economy in 2016-2023, and to show the importance and role of the SCO in solving economic issues in the region.

- Analyze the SCO and its transformation into an influential and stable regional organization;
- Provide a general geographical description of the SCO member states;
- Study the economy of the SCO member states;
- Show the importance and role of the SCO in solving economic issues in the region;
- Assess the current position and role of the SCO in the international arena;

- Show the position of Uzbekistan in the current activities of the organization;

The source base of the study is political and scientific works, scientific studies, scientific articles published in newspapers and magazines in 2016-2024.

In the study and analysis, the general-logical, systematic approach and analysis-synthesis methods of dialectics were used, as well as special historical-historical-genetic, chronological and historical comparative methods. The principles of objectivity, causality (determinism), historicity and systematicity (systematic) of historical knowledge were also used. When analyzing various sources and information, they were approached from a comparative and critical perspective. Taking into account the characteristics of the period, events were summarized and analyzed based on the methods of historicism, gradualism, and civilizational approach.

In developing the theoretical and methodological basis of the study, the scientific and theoretical guidelines put forward by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, as well as the important tasks set out in the Resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, were used.

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